

ISic1190

The municipium of the Haluntini honours Gnaeus Pollienus

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

breccia (local)

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8814

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1 : mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2 : mm

Text

1. Τὸ μουνικίπιον τῶ[ν]
2. Ἄλοντίων Γναῖον
3. Πολλιηνὸν Πολλιηνο[ῦ]
4. υἰὸν εὐεργέτη, γ' ἀπό
5. γονον εὐνοία[ς] ἔνεκ[εν]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491448

EDCS 39101554

PHI 140674

PHI 175639

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0367 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 38.0919
- Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika 6.* Palermo. At 44
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5608
- undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 193
- Cagnat, R., Toutain, J., Jouguet, P. 1906-1927. Inscriptiones Graecae ad res Romanas pertinentes. Paris. At 509
- Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 19
- Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 42 n.87, 38 n.57, fig.31

Licensed under a Creative Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1190. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351755>